

News Reading and Watching Trends of Residential Students: A Study on a Public University of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The goal of the study was to learn more about how residential students at a public university in Bangladesh consume news and watch it. The research was quantitative in character and was conducted using a survey approach that covered five university residence halls. Students from diverse schools and disciplines were included in the study's population. This study relied on a convenient sampling strategy. For this study, the students were given 225 questionnaires, of which 200 were returned. Half of the respondents prefer to read Bengali newspapers, according to the poll (Daily Prothom Alo). They chose to read the newspaper for information on world politics. They also acknowledged the importance of news reading and viewing in their daily lives. More than half of those polled share news with their friends and family or make negative comments about it while reading or viewing it. They recognize the benefits of reading and viewing the news in terms of expanding their knowledge, keeping up with the times, and changing their minds.

Keywords: *Mass Media, News Reading, and Watching, Residential Students*

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Introduction

Students are state citizens who are aware of their responsibilities. They react to political trends and social change more than any other segment of the population. Their schooling and reading habits have resulted in this awareness (Aronowitz, S., & Giroux, H. A.)

2003). A student's reading and watching habits are formed mostly during his or her childhood, high school, and college years. They have the option to practice the habit more precisely when they attend a higher educational institution such as a university. Because of the syllabus, they read more books, articles, and other forms of media. They are aided in acquiring such knowledge by the media. It's known as the 'fourth estate' (Majumdar, 2003). The newspaper is one of the most important parts of the mass media for conveying information. It is regarded as an essential component of human and social existence (Uddin, 1980) since it is essential for understanding society, history, culture, and nation. As a result, it has an impact on a country's educated and conscious citizens.

The practice of reading and watching the news broadens the student's horizons, amplifies wisdoms, and makes them widely recognized. It also encourages them to participate in any deliberations about catastrophic disasters (Aravind, S., & Chinnasamy, K. 2017). The media not only informs, but also coaches, facilitates, and persuades people to form opinions on important issues. Reading the newspaper encourages readers to seek out and enter the storehouse of information on a daily basis (Majumder & Hasan, 2013). It not only broadens our knowledge, but also helps readers better their lifestyle, thinking, and character.

Print, electronic, and internet media are examples of distinct sorts of media. Print media may be classified into numerous categories, such as newspaper, magazine, book, and so on, whereas electronic media can be classified into several forms, such as television, radio, and so on (Van Dijk, J. A. G. M., & Van Deursen, A. J. A. M. 2010). Internet journalism or new media, such as online media, are current trends in the media. Every electronic and print publication now has an online edition. As a result, individuals may watch and read the news for free or at a little cost at any time and from anywhere (Auwal, A. M., 2016). Contemporary phenomena that impart a strong sense of educational value and disseminate a wealth of information on politics, economics, entertainment, sports, business, industry, trade, and commerce, mass media are an inescapable component of knowledge acquisition. Reading and viewing news may provide students with timely and motivating information, and it can also help them develop their language skills and vocabulary. Students will also have a clear grasp of what is going on in their nation and throughout the globe (Salkind, N. J., & Rainwater, T. 2006).

There are 2,834 daily, weekly, fortnightly, monthly, tri-monthly, and sixteen monthly news outlets in Bangladesh, as well as 31 private satellite television channels, 24 FM radio stations, and 32 community radio stations (Media Landscapes, 2021).

Literature Review

Ahmed and Karim (2004) performed research on Khulna University students' newspaper and magazine reading habits. They discovered that a greater number of respondents read the newspaper on a regular basis and in a range of settings, such as the university central library, halls, messes, bookshops, and pharmacies. The university's major library and various halls house national and local media archives. Asifa (2018), on the other hand, led a research of Fisheries College students' newspaper reading habits. He screamed, "Nearly half of the students!"

(52.45 percent) read the news on a regular basis and spent less than 30 minutes doing so. The majority of students choose to read the sports and games section of the newspaper and rely on the media to keep up with current events. More than half of those polled read newspapers in print rather than online.

Akanda, Hoq, and Hasan discussed the reading patterns of students in the social sciences and arts (2013). They found that 48.67 percent of people read the newspaper for 1 to 2 hours every day, and that the majority of people read the newspaper to learn new things and broaden their perspectives. To read the newspaper, the majority of students rely on the hall libraries. The daily Prothom Alo is read by a substantial percentage of respondents, and the foreign section is preferred by 130 (12.96%) of students for getting day-to-day information. According to the survey, 43.85% of respondents read the newspaper for personal growth.

Sudha Rani (2014) reported that a considerable majority of students 53.94% read newspapers every day and they visit the library three to four times each week, spending 1-2 hours in the library. The majority of people (82.89 percent) said they preferred to read the newspaper in electronic format, which featured sections on jobs and education. Ambika (2018) reported the same conclusion, noting that the majority of students read newspapers at the library. A big number of students.

Self-subscribers of newspapers account for 46.36 percent of students, and the majority of respondents choose to read print newspapers.

The majority of participants read current affairs, career, lifestyle, sports, and business news, according to Sharma and Saini (2019). For important newspaper adverts, more

than 56% of respondents use mobile click. According to a survey of Nigerian undergraduates done by Bankole (2002), the majority of the students follow the news to discover about politics, economics, academics, and culture.

According to Asokan and Dhanavandan (2013), the majority of respondents had purchased individual newspaper subscriptions, and a high proportion of students liked to read newspapers to improve their general knowledge. In addition, Veerabasavaiah and Amaravathi (2018) found that the majority of respondents read newspapers to increase their general knowledge in their research. According to Kumar and Siddiqui, students tend to read editorial parts, followed by sports and politics (2011). The majority of individuals read the news for knowledge, and about a third read it to broaden their horizons.

According to Majumder & Hasan (2013), the majority of respondents read the newspaper for the same or less than an hour. Self-subscription is the newspaper's principal source of income. The printed copy is still the best newspaper medium for the respondents. The majority of respondents read the Daily Prothom Alo and Daily Star. Nearly half of the respondents prefer sports and entertainment news. The major purpose of reading newspaper is to improve the general knowledge of respondents.

Krishnamurthy and Awari conducted a research on newspaper reading patterns within post-graduate students at Karnatak University, Dharwad (2015). They observed that a large number of students like reading a newspaper, with the proportion of participants reading newspapers on occasion, spending less than one hour per day reading the news, and two-thirds obtaining their newspaper from home. More than half of the students read the newspaper for general news and to stay up to date on current events. More than half of the students want to read the education part of the newspaper, and more than half of the students' parents encourage them to do so. A big impediment to not reading the newspaper is a lack of time. The majority of the students prefer to read printed newspapers.

Furthermore, Edegoh, Ezeh, and Samson (2015) conducted a study in Anambra State, Nigeria, to assess the newspaper reading habits of young people. They observed that nearly half of the respondents 49% read The Sun on a daily basis, and that more than half (54%) read newspapers on a weekly basis. A significant proportion of respondents like reading sports news, and thus more than a quarter of those polled (29%) read newspapers for free at newsstands. Almost a third of those polled said they read daily newspapers on the internet or on their phone.

Research Gap

Days have changed with technical knowledge and innovation. Now this is very easy for a person to be involved with mass media for gathering information than previous time. Diversified information can be thoroughly amassed with the little knowledge of technology. Though there are a good number of research work on news reading and watching habits but it lacks to include readers interested section of the newspaper. It also covers the sharing and commenting tendencies of the news readers to spread the news very fast to their nearest and dearest ones. However, reader's opinion regarding the effect on news reading and watching on their daily life have been incorporated as a research gap.

Theoretical Framework

Uses and Gratification Theory

UGT stands for "uses and gratifications," and it's a technique of examining why and how people actively seek out certain media to suit specific needs. In 1974, Jay Blumler and Elihu Katz proposed this concept. It's a method of approaching mass communication from the audience's point of view. This communication theory is positivistic in form and focuses on mass media communication. It is founded on the socio-psychological communication tradition. UGT's main concern is: Why do people use the media and for what objectives do they utilize it? UGT looks at how people choose media for certain purposes such knowledge, leisure, social interaction /companionship, diversion, or escape.

The Uses and Gratification theory was used to perform this research. Essentially, the respondents in this research read or watch the news in order to meet a certain demand of interest, and they do it through a variety of media sources. They often utilize the media for a variety of goals, including keeping up with current events, expanding their knowledge, amusement, becoming a language expert, changing their thinking level, being more self-aware, and changing their societal view. The media performs all of these roles in order to satisfy the audience, yet it is unable to offer the information that they desire.

Media Dependency Theory

Media dependency theory is the study of the influence of mass media on audiences and the linkages between media, audiences, and social systems. It was initially presented in 1976 by Sandra Ball-Rokeach and Melvin DeFleur, two American communications professors. Dependence theory defines dependency as a relation in which a party's needs and aspirations are reliant on another's resources. The approach emphasizes the connection between media and viewers. Individuals in industrial and information-

based societies develop a dependence on the media to suit a variety of needs, ranging from a want for information about a political participant's policy views (to help voting choices) to a wish for leisure and pleasure.

The cognitive, psychological, and behavioral implications of a person's dependence on the media are the three types of effects that might arise. Cognitive influences are changes in an audience's views, beliefs, and values, especially those generated by the media's engagement in political "agenda shaping." Overexposure to news reports about violent episodes in certain neighborhoods, for example, may lead to feelings of dread and anxiety about living in such areas. Deactivation, which happens when individuals in an audience cease doing things they would have done if they hadn't been exposed to certain media messages, is an instance of a behavioral influence. It's probable that failing to vote in political elections has had an effect on this. In this communication process, the active audience chooses the medium based on their own needs as well as other factors such as economic conditions, society, and culture. If alternative sources can supply the public's needs, media reliance will be lessened.

The responders are usually engaged, and the media they use are goal-oriented, and they compete with other resources to meet their needs. Audiences are self-aware enough of their media use, interests, and reasons to offer researchers with an accurate picture of their usage.

Operational Definition

Residential students: Students who resides permanently (accommodated by university authority) in a hall or in a dormitory in the University campus.

Mass media: The term "mass media" refers to a wide range of media technologies that use mass communication to reach a broad audience. There are a multitude of venues via which this communication is carried out.

News Reading and Watching: News is information about current occurrences in the nation or overseas in a certain field of activity that is published in newspapers and aired on radio and television. Reading means going through the papers either preserved by the hall authority or by personal effort to acquire information. Watching is considered as observing news from various television channels to gather knowledge.

Objectives of the Study

To carry out this study targeted some objectives, these are the following

1. To find out the nature and types of reading and watching news by the students;
2. To know the opinion regarding the usefulness of reading and watching news;
3. To explore the opinion regarding the effect of news reading and watching;
4. To see the commenting and sharing tendencies against the news they read and watch.

Materials and Methods

The research was quantitative in character and was conducted using the survey method. The five (5) residential halls of Khulna University are Khan Jaha Ali Hall, Khan Bahadur Ahsanullah Hall, Aparajita Hall, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Hall, and Bangamata Begum Fazilatunnesa Mujib Hall, with two for female students and three for male students. The population was drawn from five Khulna University residential halls in accordance with the study's requirements. The study's participants were from several KU Schools and Disciplines. Furthermore, the population includes KU first-year, second-year, third-year, fourth-year, and master's students.

The convenience sampling approach was used to pick this research. The needed sampling size was $n=200$, with a margin of error of 0.067 with a 95 percent degree of confidence and a 4 percent standard error. This sample was taken in order for the study to be accepted. Convenience sampling and a random walk were used to verify that the sample was random and that external validity was as high as feasible.

The sample size was calculated using Yemane's formula. The sample size was calculated using Yemane's formula (1967) as follows:

$$= \frac{N}{1 + \frac{N \cdot e^2}{n}}$$

Here,

N= Total

Population n=

Sample Size

e= Confidence Interval (Marginal of Error)

2000

$$n = \frac{1}{(0.067)^2} \times 2000$$
$$= 200.44$$

n= 200 (for study purpose only)

Before starting final data collection, a pre-test was conducted to verify the reliability of the questionnaire. Data for the pre-test were collected from 50 students (two students from each discipline) of Khulna University during May, 2019. After pre-test, the questionnaire was revised and finalized for final data collection from the field. Fieldwork was conducted from the field. Fieldwork was conducted from June to July, 2019.

Results

Table1: *School-Wise Distribution of Respondents*

School name	f	%
SET school	70	35.0
Social science school	55	27.5
Arts and humanities school	25	12.5
Business and administration school	2	1.0
Life science school	35	17.5
Fine arts	7	3.5
Law school	6	3

(Source: Field survey, 2019)

Table-1 shows 35.0% students were from bachelor of SET school while second largest numbers of respondents were from Social Science School (27.5%). More than twelve percent respondents were from Arts and Humanities School, More than seventeen percent respondents were from Life Science School, three percent respondents were from Law School, and only one percent respondents were from Business and Administration School.

Table 2: *Percentage distribution of name, place of reading or watching and section of newspaper or news channel by respondents*

Name of Newspaper or News Channel	f	%
Daily Prothom Alo	100	50.0
Daily Star	30	15.0
BBC Bangla	10	5.0
Somoy TV	13	6.5
Jamuna TV	9	4.5
Others	38	20.0
Foreign newspapers		
The New York Times	17	8.5
Times of India	4	2.0
BBC	7	3.5
The Guardian	3	1.5
Others	169	85.0
Local Newspaper		
Daily Purbanchal	21	10.5

Dainik Dristipat	11	5.5
The Daily Karatoa	8	4.0
Gramer Kagoj	6	3.0
others local newspaper	49	24.5
Do not read	105	52.5
Preferred section of newspaper		
Education page	70	35.0
Entertainment page	5	2.5
International page	87	43.5
Sports	17	8.5
Others	21	10.5
Place of reading or watching news		
Hall room	79	39.5
Own room	34	17.0
Library	7	3.5
Smart phone	68	34.0
Others	12	6.0

(Source: Field survey 2019)

Table 2 reveals that the half of the respondents (50%) prefer to read Bengali newspaper (Daily Prothom Alo) while only fifteen percent of them choose to read English Dailies (Daily Star). Two fifth of the respondents (39.5%) read or watch news in the hall room while seventeen percent of them do it in their own room. Only three respondents read or watch news in library room of the hall but thirty four percent respondent read or watch news in their smart phone.

In the case of foreign news reading and watching, more than eight and three percent go through The New York Times the BBC respectively. More than half of the respondents (52.5%) respondents do not read any local newspaper. International affairs were considered as an important section to more than forty three percent students of the study whereas 'education page' was followed by thirty five percent of them. Respondents think that is important for students. Even more than eight percent respondents preferred sports section is important for students. Only two percent above respondents like to enjoy entertainment leaf.

Table 3: *Percentage distribution of utility of news reading and watching by respondents*

Usefulness of news reading and watching	f	%
Yes	182	91.0
No	18	9.0
Necessity of reading or watching the news to new generation		
Fully agree	146	73.0

Somewhat agree	35	17.5
Some agree	6	3.0
Disagree	13	6.5

(Source: Field survey, 2019)

It is expounded from Table 3 that ninety percent respondents recognized the usefulness of the newspaper in their life. In the concern to new generation, seventy three percent respondents fully agreed that the new generation has the necessity to read or watch the news of media where 'somewhat agree' was claimed by more than seventeen percent on the same issue.

Table 04: *Percentage distribution of commenting against news or sharing it to their favorite person by respondents.*

Sharing news or commenting against news	F	%
Yes	109	54.5
No	91	45.5
News Sharing		
Family	30	15.0
Relative	7	3.5
Friends	159	79.5
Others	4	2.0

(Source: Field survey 2019)

It is seen from Table 4 that more than half of the respondents (54.5%) share news or comment against the news during reading or watching news. More than seventy nine percent of them shared the news to their friends and fifteen percent to their family.

Table 5: *Percentage distribution of opinion regarding the effect of news reading and watching in the lives of the respondents*

Types of effect of news reading and watching	f	%
Increase knowledge	28	14.0
Change thinking level	9	4.5
Mental change & self-awareness	19	9.0
To update with time	33	16.5
Others changes	22	11.5
No change	89	44.5

(Source: Field survey 2019)

Table 5 shows that fourteen percent respondents admitted the effect of news reading and watching in increasing their knowledge while more than sixteen percent respondents mentioned it to be up-to-date with time. Even nine percent of them found their mental change and self-awareness as the effect of news reading and watching.

More than forty four percent did not get any changes brought about by news reading and watching.

Discussion

In this study, three-fifths of the pupils were male, while the rest were female. Two-thirds of participants read or watch news frequently, while one-fourth read or watch news often and infrequently, according to the research. Nearly half of the respondents at Khulna University read the paper, with one-fifth reading the newspaper's online version. Hasan (2013) and Majumder (2013) both arrived to the same result. According to the conclusions of the survey, one-third of respondents obtains media news in an equitable manner. More than half of the kids read or watch the news as a class activity. Three-fifths of students think watching or reading the news has had a positive impact on their lives. The media, according to the majority of the respondents (92.0 percent), should be reformed. Just about a quarter of those polled are interested in reading or watching their parents' news. Approximately 68 percent of those polled feel that online media is the most relevant in today's world. The news is shared by the great majority of respondents (88.0%), and more than half of those who read or watch the news comment on it.

To stay up with current events, the majority of participants read or watch the news (Asifa, 2018). According to the study, a large percentage of respondents read or watch the news to keep up with current events. The majority of participants do not read or watch the news through self-subscription, whereas a smaller minority do. The similar conclusion was reached by Kumar, Nagrarajan, and Prabkar (2017).

According to the findings, the majority of respondents read or watch the news for less than an hour per day, while only a minority spend 1 to 2 hours per day reading or watching the news. Majumder and Hasan (2013) frequently discovered a similar relationship. While reading and viewing the news, the audience has encountered a variety of issues. Aside from that, the survey reveals that more than one-fifth of respondents are subjected to excessive advertising and low-quality newspaper material. This remark conflicts with Kumar, Nagrarajan, and Prabkar (2017), who said that the most common issues that respondents confront are slow internet speeds and insufficient newspaper copies in the library.

The majority of respondents prefer to read newspapers in Bangla (Majumder and Hasan, 2013). A similar finding may be seen in this investigation. Half of respondents prefer reading Daily Prothom Alo, whereas the other half likes to read Daily Star, according to the data. Majumder and Hasan identified a similar link (2013). Two-thirds of male participants read or watch the news, while more than half of female respondents (56.0 percent) do as well. Newspapers are still important in the digital age,

according to the majority of the respondents (91.0 percent). More than a third of those polled prefer to read or watch news on their phone, while over two-fifths prefer reading or watch news in the hallway.

Conclusion

Their practice of reading and watching the news can help them become excellent citizens who can give for themselves and their country whenever it is needed. Students are a country's future. The habit of reading and viewing the news is linked to the entire learning growth process, and success in learning is dependent on good reading. Reading habits, knowledge, and awareness may all be improved with the aid of the media. The mass media not only provide current news, but also a variety of other sorts of information to the public, such as instructive articles, social features, editorials, sub-editorials, country economic situation, assessments, and observations. In today's extremely competitive world, the mass media can provide students with the required information, expertise, and insights to help them succeed not just in competitive tests or job interviews, but also in their professional and social lives. Reading and viewing the news improves communication and creative abilities, as well as providing readers with an unbiased and educated viewpoint. News reading and viewing are important parts of education and self-development since they help with communication skills, altering lifestyles, developing general knowledge, language proficiency, and current global information. As a result, reading and watching the news is deemed necessary for university students.

Authors' Contributions

The project was conceptualized by Samrat Shaikh, and the research was overseen by Mamunor Rashid. Md. Ripul Kabir contributed to the literature review, discussion section, and finalization of the article, while Samrat Shaikh did the data collecting, statistical analysis, and wrote the initial draft, which included findings and tables. The final document was read and approved by all of the writers.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations are critical in any research because they guarantee that respondents provide truthful information without fear or reluctance. The aims and objectives of the research were first given to the participants, who have been assured that their knowledge would be used strictly for the study's purposes. Participants were advised that their participation in the research was purely optional and that they might opt out at any time.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendix: Questionnaire

<p align="center">News Reading and Watching Trends of Residential Students: A Study on a Public University of Bangladesh</p> <p align="center">The research is only used to academic purpose and the privacy of your information will be protected.</p> <p align="center">(Primary information of Respondent)</p>			
Name:		Gender: Male Female	year:
Discipline:		Father profession:	
Year:		Mather profession:	
School:		Monthly income of family:	
Hall		Mobile or Email No:	

1. How is your tendency to watch or read news?

a) Regular b) Irregular c) Now and Then d) Sometimes

1.1 When do you start to read or watch the news?

Ans:

2. Which medium do you used to read or watch the news?

a) Newspapers b) Online portal c) Television d) YouTube e) Facebook link

2.1 Where do you read or watch the news?

a) Hall room b) Own room c) Library d) Smart phone e) Others medium

2.2 When do you read or watch the news?

a) When the time comes b) Evening c) Morning d) Night

3. Do you read the newspaper by purchase?

a) Yes b) No

3.1 What types of news do you prefer to read?

a) Sports b) Entertainment c) Politics d) International e) Others

3.2 How many times do you spend to read or watch the news?

a) 0-30 minutes b) 30 minutes-1hour c) 1-2 hours d) 2-2 more hours

4. Do you read any foreign newspapers?

a) Yes b) No

4.2 If yes, the name of the foreign newspaper.

Ans:

5. Why do you read or watch the news?

a) To increase knowledge b) To entertainment c) Habitual d) To update with time

6. What is your opinion about publish news of mass media?

a) Fully accepted b) Some accepted c) Fairly acceptable d) Not accepted

6.1 Can change society by reading the news of mass media?

a) Yes b) No

6.2 Are any newspapers publish in your district? If published, the name of newspaper.

Ans:

7.1 Does the media spread the rumor? What do you think?

a) Sometimes b) Yes c) No

7.2 Does any use of the magazine in the present digital age?

a) Yes b) No

8. Do you read or watch the news as a part of the academic activity?

a) Yes b) No

8.1. Does have any necessity to read or watch the news of the new generation, what is your opinion about this?

a) Fully agree with b) somewhat agree c) Some agree d) Disagree

9. Do you have taken any newspaper at your house?

a) Yes b) No

10. Which language prefers to read the newspapers?

a) Bengali b) English c) Both language

11. Do you have any change in your life? If have changed, which type of change write below.

Ans:

12. Which newspaper or news channel do you prefer to read or

watch? Ans:

13. Do you face any problem to read or watch the news?

- a) Yes b) No

13.1 If yes, what type of problems do you face?

- a) Extra advertisement b) Language problem c) Low standard of newspapers d) Others

14. Do you share news to anyone that you read or watch?

- a) Yes b) No

14.1 If yes, to whom?

- a) Family b) Relative c) Friends d) Others

15. Do you share or comment to read or watch the news?

- a) Yes b) No

15.1 Do you click on page of any newspaper or news channel in the social media?

- a) Yes b) No

16. Which news medium is most suitable in digital age?

- a) Print media b) Electronic media c) Online media

17. Do you read any column or article of any newspaper?

- a) Yes b) No

17.1 If yes, how many newspaper's column does you read?

- a) One b) Two c) Three d) More

18. Does have any necessity of Renovation of current mass media?

- a) Yes b) No

19. Who inspire you to read or watch the news?

- a) Parents b) Teachers c) Friends d) Others

20. Which pages are important for students?

- a) Education page b) Entertainment page c) International page
d) Sports e) Others.